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MODERN QUIT INDIA MOVEMENT: THE STORY OF NET NEUTRALITY AND FREE BASICS IN INDIA

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Abstract

The Internet has now become an obligatory instrument for the users around the world and a fundamental facilitator of innovation and economic, cultural, political and social growth. India has a large number of Internet users who can access the Internet without being restricted to access certain sites. This is because of Net Neutrality, a concept according to which all the data should be treated equal or in other words all the contents should be accessible to the user freely, without giving preference in speed or pricing to any particular set of content. In February 2015, Facebook owner Mark Zuckerberg came to India with an offer named internet.org, which was later rechristened to Free Basics. According to this concept Internet will be free in India and the poor will be benefitted due to it. But, only the sites that will partner with facebook can be accessed and facebook will act as the gatekeeper, snooping into customer's personal data. It means people will only be able to see what facebook wants us to and even can refrain us from something on the internet if it goes against them. This is a complete violation of the Right to Freedom of Speech and Expression which the Indian Constitution has given to its citizens. Free Basics was basically a kind of electronic fascism and a diktat on people's individual right. The activists of net neutrality, joined by the general masses and many start-ups, smelled capitalism in this whole concept and came out to protest. The battle was won, net neutrality won, they made Free Basics Quit India. This paper attempts to understand the basic concept of Net Neutrality and Free Basics. It further tries to explain how the concept of capitalism was embedded in Facebook's veiled idea of free basics and will also try to look into how the supporters of Net Neutrality created a modern day Quit India Movement.

Key Words: Net Neutrality; facebook; Free Basics; Capitalism;

Introduction

Unlike the days when the West made colonies to look for spices or expand their market, in the era of globalization, the West found a more sophisticated way of invisibly colonizing the erstwhile colonies by the method of addicting the people of what we today call or what we today cannot live without- “The Internet”. It has become an indispensable tool for the day to day work; for the evolution and advancement of a country’s polity, economy and society. Talking about India, an agricultural country, a handful of the villagers use the internet, while most of it is used by the urban population, semi-urban people as well as the intelligentsia. Internet is a competitive market and the Indian network providers often fear that increased revenue might hinder the competition and affect them.

A few months back, active social media users came across two words very often- Internet.org or Free Basics and Net Neutrality. This issue was debated and we even saw our Prime Minister Narendra Modi visiting Facebook owner Mark Zukerberg. The debate was followed by protests against Free Basics, where people resorted to the internet as well as came down to the streets to show their support in favour of Net Neutrality. The debate turned such ugly that people sided with what they believed in was good for their future and came up with their arguments. So what is this Net Neutrality and Free Basics? This paper will try to explain the basics of these two terms and try to examine how the concept of capitalism was embedded in Facebook’s veiled idea of free basics and will also try to look into how the supporters of Net Neutrality created a modern day Quit India Movement.

Network Neutrality or ‘Net neutrality’:-

We use the internet daily without being restricted any access to any site. Have we ever thought how are we able to do so? The answer is simple- Net Neutrality. Net Neutrality has helped to keep the free and open characteristic of the Internet intact in India. Net Neutrality is basically a concept according to which all the data should be treated equal or in other words all the contents should be accessible to the user freely, without giving preference in speed or pricing to any particular set of content. In India The Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI) established by the Telecom Regulatory Act of India, 1997, looks after the telecom industry . Open internet

is basically a platform for freedom of expression and economic growth, but once a part of this platform is caged, information that will be accessible will be limited and we will be dictated of what contents to access. It is the duty of the Internet Service Providers (ISPs) to provide accessibility to all websites equally without discriminating on the price or the source or destination. Let us take an example to make this point clear. If a person is having 1 GB of free data, he can use it according to his wish. He may access youtube, facebook, go through educational sites, etc. The ISPs have no right to intervene if this particular person is watching youtube or downloading movies as it consumes data faster. The supporters of free internet have even compared free internet to electricity, like if a person is paying for a certain amount of electricity, the provider will in no way look as to how that person is consuming it- by using fan, air conditioner or by charging his phone. We internet users really spent a happy time on the internet as it gives a hassle free life; even for the basics questions we don't really open a book but Google search it. So, what if we are denied this option of accessing all the sites, denied getting answers for all our questions, denied our basic right to knowledge? These questions haunted a large number of internet users when Mark Zukerberg came up with his idea of internet.org.

Free Basics: A kind of *diktat*:-

Ever since the idea of internet.org was introduced in India in February 2015, Indian newspapers and roadside hoardings hosted the advertisement calling for support to this particular idea flaunting pictures of men, women and children, trying to beam an idea woven around the concept that by supporting internet.org people will be entitled to free internet, which will also help the Indian poor in connecting to the world. Around Rs. 300 crore was spent for this ad campaign or to say facebook spent such a huge amount to sell its lie. Can opening the newspaper in the morning or while walking down the street and coming across such advertisement lure the Indian masses? Although a good number of people got lured by this free offer from facebook, a large number of the people smelled capitalism in it. They could clearly foresee a diktat, a kind of Information Technological fascism in this offer. Soon after in September, the internet.org was

rechristened Free Basics, just a few days before Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi's visit to Facebook's headquarter at Mark Zuckerberg's invitation. First let us try to understand the concept of Free Basics according to the Facebook version. According to Facebook, it is an open platform that gives Indian developers the opportunity to make their websites and services available free of charge to the people who cannot afford internet access, but this free access is limited to partner websites and applications.¹ It was launched two years ago globally in partnership with Samsung, Ericsson, Media Tek, Opera Software, Nokia and Qualcomm.² In India, the Free Basics found its partner in Reliance Telecommunication. During the last half of the previous year, customers using Reliance came across a Free button on their Facebook. India is already such a country which is divided on the issue of caste and now the white skinned capitalist wanted to divide the Indians more through telecom services. The partnership meant that the partner Reliance will be paid with a bandwidth so that Facebook and a set of other sites are offered for free, whereas the charges for straying elsewhere on the internet was the partner company's decision. Through Free Basics, the only motive of Facebook was to act as the gatekeeper, giving access to the users of certain sites. Though Zuckerberg argued that this would mean free internet for the Indian poor, but the main question that arises is that what is the significance behind this idea? Only to tell the poor that Facebook and a set of websites which have partnered with Facebook is the whole internet? This is no kind of a free internet or rather any kind of charity, which Zuckerberg tried to prove, the whole concept is nothing less than a diktat- something which dictates the users of what to use and what to see. In short a complete annihilation of freedom on the internet. By putting a restriction to access all the sites, Free Basics violates the principle of Net Neutrality. This also means that the new and emerging small scale websites, developers and applications cannot enter into the free market competition of the internet. Facebook next came up with a second campaign by tricking the people to vote in favour of Free Basics. This was done by instituting the 'Save Free Basics' campaign according to which through one click a user can send a templated email to the regulator from his/her account saying that the user was in favour of Free Basics. The problem was that this campaign started working against Net Neutrality and in favour of Free Basics as half of the social media users clicked without understanding the whole concept

¹ Anita Babu, *10 Things to know about Facebook's Free Basics, net neutrality*, Business Standard (23/12/2015), available at www.business-standard.com/article/companies/10-things-to-know-about-facebook-s-free-basics-net-neutrality-115122300326_1.html, last seen on 10/04/2016.

² Ibid.

of this veiled term. This was mainly because this particular population either did not have the time to understand or did not want to understand this particular concept. They were only lured by the term 'Free'. Moreover, if Free Basics would have been implemented, not only would it have curtailed the right to access all the websites, but also it would have led to the restriction on Freedom of Speech and Expression. Article 19 (1)a in the Constitution of India 1949, mentions about the Right to Freedom of Speech and Expression. By this right an Indian citizen can express his views by the method of speaking/ use of verbal words, writing books, articles, pamphlets or even on the internet, printing, use of banners, signs etc. But, if facebook would have been allowed to be the gatekeeper, it would have kept a good amount of vigilance on certain websites, posts and people on the internet. If something went against them, that particular source/ website would have been restricted from reaching the masses. In other words, only those information would have come down to us, which facebook and its partners wanted us to know. The general masses would have been the victims of a kind of electronic fascism and the start-up companies would have been the victims of economic hegemony. But, a large number of social media users came out in favour of net neutrality by using the weapons/ right of freedom of speech and expression and protests and ultimately they were successful in driving this concept out of Indian internet. They made free basics Quit India.

It's all about Capitalism:-

Investments from the metropolis in India, beginning early 19th century led to the transition of the pre-capitalist economy into an industry dominated economy. Capitalism gradually crept in the heart of the colony, but India did not herself taste the benefits of capitalism. With time capitalism has accommodated different kinds of elements in its garb and has itself changed its nature. In the era of globalization capitalism has found a new mode of hegemonizing the world and that is through the internet. In fact, 'Internet' is the best thing that has happened to capitalism. As already mentioned Free Basics will give facebook the right to act as the gatekeeper and all the traffic will go via facebook servers. Most importantly, facebook will have the right to snoop into the customer data. Mark Zuckerberg in a post on his personal facebook

page wrote that “We know that connecting them can help lift people out of poverty, create millions of jobs and spread education opportunities. We care about these people, and that’s why we are so committed to connecting them.”³ By reading this status update cannot we really say that Mark Zuckerberg is trying to be the modern Alexander the Great? Once this Greek ruler wanted to conquer the whole world, similarly Mark is trying to conquer the whole world by just connecting it at the nick of a click. Analysing Zuckerberg’s facebook post and his ad campaigns in India a few question arises. Firstly, India is such a country where there are still villages where electricity has not yet reached. Consequently, when people does not have the option of light and are dependent on oil lamps and candles, how can they be expected to own a smart phone and charge it, then use the Free Basics. Secondly, in the past few months there have been above the average cases of farmer suicides in the country due to poverty. So is Zuckerberg really expecting these poor people, who do not have the money to buy two meals a day to own a smart phone? Recently, in Bundelkhand the poverty level has reached such a point that people are compelled to drink water from the open pits and chapattis made of grass. Thirdly, illiteracy rate is high in the rural areas in India and can we really expect them to be tech savy? Fouthly, the main problem that India faces is that of Caste. India is already divided on the issue of caste and communal lines. By offering access to only a few websites with Facebook as the gatekeeper, Indians will be further divided. In the garb of offering free internet, an idea of E-Colonialism stands at the highest stage of this whole concept of Free Basics. Currently, developed countries appear to dominate the internet with the developing world in the sidelines; this is revealed by an unthinking search of the Internet while the most websites are in English language and are generally sourced from the United States.⁴ If measures are not used to locate sites in the developing world and to establish them as an information providers, most developing countries may become ‘electronic colonies’ that are force-fed generated by the developed world.⁵ The impact of e-colonialism can potentially be just as devastating as that of mercantile colonialism in the 19th century.⁶

³ Vindu Goel and Mike Issac, *Facebook Loses a Battle in India Over Its Free Basics Program*, New York Times (8/2/2016), available at www.nytimes.com/2016/02/09/business/facebook-loses-a-battle-in-india-over-its-free-basics-program.html?_r=0, last seen on 10/04/2016.

⁴ V.S Venkatesan and Neetha Nambiar, *The New Challenge of the 21st Century*, Idea Group Publishing, 778, available at www.irma-international.org/viewtitle/32140/, last seen on 10/04/2016.

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Ibid., 779.

We have often heard the word ‘free’. But can any commodity come to us for free and if yes, then under what circumstances? This can be explained by the concept of post-scarcity economics. It holds that goods or services that can be produced by the minimum effort or labour can be given out for free. It means that if everything is in abundance and no longer scarce then it will be free. But the post scarcity economics is considered to be utopian. So, is the whole concept of Free Basics utopian or is there any hidden motive of capitalism in it? Has the internet come to that point where it can be given out for free? The whole idea of free basics can be interpreted in a way that Mark Zuckerberg had quite well understood that in the near future internet was going to be cheap. That would have had given a good amount of blow to his business. If his Free Basic plan would have been successful in India, maybe in the near future he would have imposed a good amount of revenue. Capitalism only understands the language of profit. So, the whole concept of Free Basics was utopian and Zuckerberg tried to sell this utopian idea to the Indian poor.

Well known philosopher, environment activist and eco-feminist Vandana Shiva rightly narrates the capitalism behind the whole idea of free basics. She writes, *95% of cotton in India is Monsanto’s proprietary Bt cotton. This year, in regions from Punjab to Karnataka, 80% of this Bt crop failed- that’s 76% of Bt cotton, farmers were left with no crop at harvest time. If, they had a choice, they would switch. But, what resembles a choice between cotton seeds is the same Bt cotton seed, marketed by the different companies under some different names, purchased in a kind of desperation as farmers try combination after combination of seeds, pesticides, herbicides, fungicides-all of which have some chemical names which are designed to make a person feels inadequate -until a person has no choice left but to take your own life..... What Monsanto has done by pushing Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) laws and patents on seeds, Zuckerberg is attempting to do to internet freedom in India and like Monsanto, he is targeting the most marginalised Indians.....The Monsanto- a kind of Facebook connection is very deep one. The top twelve investors of Monsanto are almost the same as the 12 investors in Facebook, including the Vanguard Group. The Vanguard Group is also a top investor in John*

*Deere, Monsanto's new partner for small tractors, bringing food production and consumption from seed to data under the control of a handful of investors.*⁷

For beginners India, Net objectivity has vast implications, particularly for start-ups many of whom are dependent on the medium for the success of their business. While Zuckerberg was busy selling his utopian ideas to the Indian masses, one of the facebook board member and a venture capitalist Marc Andreessen wrote on Twitter that “Anti-colonialism has been economically calamitous for the people in India for a long time, Why stop now?”⁸ while the post was later deleted, yet it offended the Indian masses. In simple terms, the post suggested India was prophesied for economic disaster by banning the initiative.

Therefore, once the main reason behind Facebook's Free Basics initiative came to the fore front more and more people joined those who were already fighting in support of Net Neutrality. Let us now try to understand how the people of India fought against this giant capitalist and made them leave India, they proved that they are the descendants of that country who made the colonial rulers leave India in the 20th century.

Modern Quit India: The fight against E-colonialism:-

As already mentioned, capitalism has changed its nature in the era of globalisation, so as the anti-colonial struggles. Since, now colonialism has become limited to economic imperialism and electronic colonialism, people have found new modes of protest to combat these giant capitalists. As the New York Times noted, Facebook's multi-million dollar advertising spree in India did nothing to convince Indians about the qualities of Free fundamentals and as a substitute fostered the attitude that facebook was only trying to carve out a permanent place for itself in India's telecom landscape, instead of improving internet access with large.⁹ Not only that viewing the internet through Facebook's selective lens would have people looking at web through blue tinted

⁷ Vandana Shiva, *Free Basics: Corporate Freedom to Privatise India's Basic Economy*, CounterCurrents.org, available at www.countercurrents.org/shiva301215.htm, last seen on 10/04/2016.

⁸ Adrienne Lafrance, *Facebook and the New Colonialism*, The Atlantic (11/2/ 2016), available at www.theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2016/02/facebook-and-the-new-colonialism/462393, last seen on 10/04/2016.

⁹ Jordan Peason, *Why Net Neutrality Abroad Is Actually Anti-colonialism?*, motherboard.vice.com, available at motherboard.vice.com/read/free-basics-facebook-net-neutrality-india-anti-colonialism, last seen on 10/04/2016.

glass. Though the idea of Free Basics took birth within the air conditioned walls of the American headquarters, yet the tinted glass that it tried to provide to the Indians was not acceptable. The language of net-neutrality was used by India's regulators in decision making, and the result was no doubtedly anti-colonial, it rejected the expansion of a massive , multinational, U.S based company and its impositions on culture and infrastructure.¹⁰ Therefore, the pro net neutrality activists and supporters started a fight against the concept of Free Basics, which has been interpreted here as the modern Quit India movement. Why this struggle has been termed here as modern Quit India calls for explanation here. First of all the popular 1942 movement was a spontaneous one, so as the case of the movement against Free Basics. The 1942 Quit India movement witnessed unusual both on account of the magnitude of popular participation and the lack of clear directives from the Congress High Command, as well as for the articulation of anger and 'hatred' against British rule, the movement brought the subjects of British India and the states' people in a joint action against the Raj.¹¹ Similarly, the movement against free basics saw thousands coming on to the streets, writing on twitter and the irony is posting updates on facebook as well. The common hatred and anger against the concept of Free Basics or more simply, the end of Internet freedom brought people from different regions, castes and communities together. Let us first attempt to understand the various modes of protest that were undertaken by the activists.

- 1) The medium of Twitter:- This platform was the most commonly used one, and was used mainly by those who could not themselves come down to the streets and protest. People even did not restrain themselves from writing terms such as #bharatchodo #vandemataram and #inquilabzindabad. These were common terms used during the struggle for independence and such use of terms can be again seen as a mode of protest against Free Basics and in support of net neutrality.
- 2) Making parody of the Free Basic advertisement of Facebook:- The last part of 2015 witnessed many parodies of the mentioned ads on facebook itself and even on magazine covers.
- 3) Sending of urgent petitions to TRAI:- When Facebook learned that it was going to lose the battle and was already at the receiving end from net neutrality supporters, especially the Save

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ Ishita Banerjee Dubey, *A History of Modern India*, 402 (1st ed., 2015).

the Internet crusaders, it launched “Send a Mail to TRAI to save Free Basics” campaign asking users to send signed templated emails to TRAI in support of the campaign. But, Indians were also not behind. They sent counter petitions to TRAI against Free Basics. Faculties of IITS, IISC and CEOs of nine Indian start up companies sent their petitions urgently to TRAI to save Net Neutrality.

- 4) Writing Blog Posts:- people took to their blogs to write about the economics of Free Basics and why it was important to save NET Neutrality in India.
- 5) Running Save the Internet Ads on Tv:- The company PayTM took the initiative for running Save the Internet Ads on Tata Sky and Dish Tv.
- 6) Protesting on the Streets:- This is perhaps the method people have resorted to for centuries. India’s technological hub Bangalore organized protests and several start up companies joined in. India’s Net Neutrality activists rallied first in thousands, then ten thousands and eventually millions under the banner and marched on the streets, terrorized companies that partnered with Facebook, one was starring their apps till the time they pulled out.¹² They were not agreed to accept Facebook’s claims of charity and development, pointing to Wikipidea’s experiment in Sub-Saharan countries which finally ended up by providing light reading for the country’s elites during the time of commutes, but it was not reaching significant number of the poor people they were aiming for and India’s net fighters sent back to the drawing board.¹³

India is the second largest market for facebook after The United States and Zukerberg had no intentions of losing it. The Quit India Movement did, however, make ‘the ruling elite aware of the possible strength of any future congress movement’ that could shake the empire’s foundation.¹⁴ Similar was the protest in the 21st century that the capitalist giant became aware of the possible future severe form of protest and the harm it can cause. The positive outcome of this whole movement was that around 1.1 million people mailed to TRAI in favour of Net Neutrality. In response to these mails send to TRAI, the Parliamentary Standing Committee on Information Technology agreed to examine the issue . In May 2015, The Department of

¹² ‘Poor Internet for Poor people’ India’s activists fight Facebook’s connection plan, the guardian, available at www.theguardian.com/world/2016/jan/15/india-net-neutrality-activists-facebook-free-basics, last seen on 10/04/2016.

¹³ The guardian, Op.cit.

¹⁴ Ishita Banerjee Dubey, Op.cit.

Telecommunication (DoT) released a report in favour of Net Neutrality mentioning that the core principles of Net Neutrality must be adhered to and the user right on the Internet must be protected-so that the service providers are not able to restrict their ability to access any service on the Internet.¹⁵

Amidst the chaos going on in India in favour and in absence of net neutrality, TRAI emerged as the modern Gandhi. It made the bold step in favour of net neutrality in India by releasing a 15 paper article called “Prohibition of Discriminatory Tariffs for Data Services Regulations”, that effectively bans services such as Free Basics. On 8th February 2016 afternoon prominent Indian venture capitalist Mahesh Murthy, who was from the beginning a supporter of Net Neutrality wrote on his Facebook page “ On differential pricing and Facebook Free Basics or Airtel Zero....They’re all banned! We won!”¹⁶ Just minutes before his announcement TRAI said that differential pricing for accessing content on the internet or what opponents of it call the absence of Net Neutrality will be treated as illegal and attract a fine up to Rs. 50 Lakh if violated.¹⁷ At last the battle in favour of Net Neutrality was won. The struggle against e-colonialism by the American capitalist giant was won.

Conclusion:-

India is a country which faces two main problems-poverty and caste. Another sub-problem is a sub-periphery (North East) within the periphery (India). To eradicate poverty the government either places a deaf ear or even if they take steps in the form of rationing shops, BPL cards etc., corruption rules. Poor people continue to remain poor. The problem of caste which started way back during the later vedic times still finds its place in the subcontinent. Untouchability is still practiced in the era of globalization, dalits are tortured and even media has become biased. If a dalit girl is raped hardly media covers it. But if a so called general category girl gets raped there is full media coverage, people come down on the streets. There is reservation for the scheduled caste and schedule tribes in India but how many of these do

¹⁵ NET NEUTRALITY DoT Committee Report (May 2015), available at [dot.gov.in/sites/default/files/u10/Net_Neutrality_Committee_report%20\(1\).pdf](http://dot.gov.in/sites/default/files/u10/Net_Neutrality_Committee_report%20(1).pdf), last seen on 11/04/2016.

¹⁶ Kalyan Subramani, *How Zuckerberg's Free Basics lost to Net Neutrality in India*, Hindustan Times (11/02/2016), available at www.hindustantimes.com/business/how-mark-zuckerberg-s-free-basics-lost-to-net-neutrality-in-india/story-31LtjWflqgBarLhwAOOWvk.html, last seen on 10/04/2016.

¹⁷ Ibid.

the actual needs of the rural areas get? Another problem is the issue of racism which the north eastern people face in north India. Nepalis are referred to as chinkis or Chinese, questions are raised on their culture. These are the problems which the common masses as well as the poor faces in India. The issue of dalit tortures, tortures on the students of various universities by their authorities, the crimes on north eastern people in Delhi, Mumbai and even now in Kolkata come down to us because of net neutrality. Today's young generation mostly find the internet comfortable for reading news, rather than that traditional methods of radio, or printed newspapers. In absence of Net Neutrality our basic knowledge will be limited. Most importantly, research will get a hard hit in India in absence of Net Neutrality. If all the websites are not accessible then subjectivity will rule research in India. Moreover, this kind of restriction will also disrespect the constitution. Part IV Article 38 (1) states that "The State shall strive to promote the welfare of the people by securing and protecting as effectively as it may be a social order in which the justice, social, economic and the political, will inform all the other institutions of the national life". Restrictions on accessibility of websites and snooping into customer's personal data and information is a violation of this particular article.

In North Bengal, tea plantations are closing down. Do Zukerberg really expect that these people will get jobs by having free internet. They are unskilled casual workers employed for plucking tea leaves. Hardly they are literate, some of them can just write their names or others uses thumb impressions. Their poverty level has reached such a situation that they are even sending their girls to flesh trade. Can free internet solve their problem? This was just an example in an attempt to portray the real problems of India, which Zukerberg's utopian promises cannot fulfil. Moreover, government has started providing free wifi to its citizens. For example, Kolkata has certain wifi zones where any person can go and access whatever they want. This initiative is spreading to other cities and states also and in near future government will themselves offer free internet. We Indians really do not need foreign capitalists to teach us what to access. The best thing about this whole net neutrality versus free basics debate and the movement against free basics was that years back in 1947 a battle against colonialism was won, and today in 2016 another battle against modern colonialism is won.

References:-

1. Anita Babu, *10 Things to know about Facebook's Free Basics, net neutrality*, Business Standard (23/12/2015), available at www.business-standard.com/article/companies/10-things-to-know-about-facebbok-s-free-basics-net-neutrality-115122300326_1.html, last seen on 10/04/2016.
2. Vindu Goel and Mike Issac, *Facebook Loses a Battle in India Over Its Free Basics Program*, New York Times (8/2/2016), available at www.nytimes.com/2016/02/09/business/facebook-loses-a-battle-in-india-over-its-free-basics-program.html?_r=0, last seen on 10/04/2016.
3. Kalyan Subramani, *How Zukerberg's Free Basics lost to Net Neutrality in India*, Hindustan Times (11/02/2016), available at www.hindustantimes.com/business/how-mark-zukerberg-s-free-basics-lost-to-net-neutrality-in-india/story-31LtjWflqgBarLhwAOOWvk.html, last seen on 10/04/2016.
4. V.S Venkatesan and Neetha Nambiar, *The New Challenge of the 21st Century*, Idea Group Publishing, 778, available at www.irma-international.org/viewtitle/32140/, last seen on 10/04/2016.
5. Vandana Shiva, *Free Basics: Corporate Freedom to Privatise India's Basic Economy*, CounterCurrents.org, available at www.countercurrents.org/shiva301215.htm, last seen on 10/04/2016.
6. Adrienne Lafrance, *Facebook and the New Colonialism*, The Atlantic (11/2/ 2016), available at www.theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2016/02/facebook-and-the-new-colonialism/462393, last seen on 10/04/2016.
7. Jordan Peason, *Why Net Neutrality Abroad Is Actually Anti-colonialism?*, motherboard.vice.com, available at motherboard.vice.com/read/free-basics-facebook-net-neutrality-india-anti-colonialism, last seen on 10/04/2016.
8. *'Poor Internet for Poor people' India's activists fight Facebook's connection plan*, the guardian, available at www.theguardian.com/world/2016/jan/15/india-net-neutrality-activists-facebook-free-basics, last seen on 10/04/2016.

9. NET NEUTRALITY DoT Committee Report (May 2015), available at [dot.gov.in/sites/default/files/u10/Net_Neutrality_Committee_report%20\(1\).pdf](http://dot.gov.in/sites/default/files/u10/Net_Neutrality_Committee_report%20(1).pdf), last seen on 11/04/2016.
10. Ishita Banerjee Dubey, *A History of Modern India*, 402 (1st ed., 2015).